

STUDIES IN INDIGOID DYES. PART XVIII. THIOINDIGOID DYES DERIVED FROM FLUORENE-2-SULPHONIC ACID

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Hitherto-unknown 4:5-fluoreno-3-hydroxy-1-thiophene, prepared from fluorene-2-sulphonic acid, has been condensed with various *o*-diketones, and the corresponding thioindigoid dyes have been obtained with a view to studying colour and its relation to chemical constitution.

Thioindigoid dyes derived from diphenyl-4-sulphonic acid were studied previously (Part XIII, this *Journal*, 1954, 31, 827). In the present communication a study of similar dyes, derived from fluorene-2-sulphonic acid, has been made so that a comparison as regards the colour and dyeing properties between these two series of compounds could now be made. So far as the dyeing properties are concerned, it has been found that the dyes derived from diphenyl-4-sulphonic acid are superior in producing a deeper and fuller shade on cotton to those derived from fluorene-2-sulphonic acid, the latter, as a class, are found feebly soluble in alkaline hydrosulphite, and thus these produce a light shade. As regards the depth of colour, there is a slight difference, the fluoreno compounds appearing slightly deeper. A study of absorption spectra of these dyes will be the subject of a later communication when a definite conclusion could be arrived at.

For the preparation of 4:5-fluoreno-3-hydroxy-1-thiophene, fluorene-2-sulphonic acid, prepared according to Hodgkinson and Mathews (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 166), was as usual converted successively into the sulphochloride, the mercaptan and the thioglycollic acid, all unknown, and this thioglycollic acid through its acid chloride was cyclised to the thioindoxyl. This thioindoxyl was then condensed with *o*-diketones for the preparation of these thioindigoid dyes. The bis-indigo was obtained as a bluish violet precipitate in small quantity by oxidising the indoxyl in alkaline solution with potassium ferricyanide. As the yield had been very small it was not further investigated. The crude, easily oxidisable thioindoxyl was dissolved in acetic acid and the acetic acid solution used for condensation with various *o*-diketones. The yield of the dyes has been fair in most of the cases. These dyes are insoluble in alcohol, slightly soluble in acetic acid and highly soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. In concentrated sulphuric acid they dissolve with a characteristic colour. They are not much soluble in alkaline hydrosulphite so that a light shade on cotton has generally been obtained.

The formation of a new five-membered ring due to the cyclisation of fluorene-2-thioglycollic acid may take place either in position-1 or 3 of the fluorene ring, but as in the formation of disubstitution products of fluorene from 2-substituted mono-compounds the position-1 is attacked and 2:1-disubstitution products are obtained, it is presumed that in the formation of thioindoxyl in this case, position-1 has similarly been attacked and 4:5-fluoreno-3-hydroxy-1-thiophene has been obtained.

The structures of the indoxyl (I), the indigoid dyes (II), and the glyoxal compound (III) may therefore be represented as :

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluorene-2-sulphonic Acid.—Fluorene (16.6 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (75 c.c.) at room temperature and to this under ice-cooling a solution of chlorosulphonic acid (12 g.) in chloroform (30 c.c.) was added in small portions with vigorous shaking. The mixture became greenish and gradually the monosulphonic acid separated out as a dirty white precipitate. After allowing to stand for an hour at room temperature and frequent shaking, the mixture was filtered from chloroform and the residue boiled with water and filtered hot. The filtrate was then mixed with potassium carbonate till slightly alkaline, boiled and filtered. The filtrate on cooling separated white crystals of the potassium salt. It was recrystallised from hot water, yield 19 g.

Fluorene-2-sulphochloride.—Carefully dried and finely powdered potassium fluorene-2-sulphonate (50 g.) was mixed with PCl₅ (50 g.) and POCl₃ (20 c.c.) and heated in an oil-bath at 140° for an hour. POCl₃ was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residue decomposed by ice and left overnight. The residue, after thoroughly washing with water and drying, was crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 139° (with previous shrinking at 155°); yield of crude sulphochloride, 40 g. (Found: C, 58.73; H, 3.52. C₁₃H₉O₂ClS requires C, 58.98; H, 3.4 per cent).

Fluorene-2-thiol was prepared by reducing the sulphochloride with tin and HCl and heating the mixture for 10 hours. Some quantity of the thiol volatilised and collected as white shining flakes in the inner tube of the condenser. The residue, after cooling, was filtered, washed with HCl (conc.) and water, and extracted with benzene; the benzene extract was dried by anhydrous calcium chloride, filtered and the benzene distilled off. The residue was then crystallised from alcohol as yellowish white flakes, m.p. 127°, yield 80-85%. (Found: C, 78.53; H, 5.18. C₁₃H₉S requires C, 78.8; H, 5.05 per cent).

Fluorene-2-thioglycollic Acid.—The above thiol (10 g.) was dissolved in 10% caustic soda solution (50 c.c.) and to this after filtration was added a solution of mono-chloroacetic acid (5 g.), previously neutralised with caustic soda. The mixture was heated on a water-bath for an hour. The sodium salt of the thioglycollic acid, which had separated out, was dissolved in a large volume of water by heating, filtered hot and the filtrate immediately acidified with HCl. The thioglycollic acid was thus precipitated as a white crystalline mass. It was then crystallised from dilute alcohol as shining flakes, m.p. 143-44°, yield 9 g. While drying it turned brownish. (Found: C, 69.81; H, 4.75. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2S$ requires C, 70.31; H, 4.68 per cent).

4:5-*Fluoreno-3-hydroxy-1-thiophene* (I).—The preceding acid (2 g.) was suspended in petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°, 20 c.c.) and to this was added PCl_5 (2 g.) and pyridine (2 drops), and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for an hour, when most of the solid went into solution. The clear solution after filtration was cooled in a refrigerator when an oil, first separated, gradually solidified to a crystalline mass, m.p. 85°. When prepared on a large scale, the oil could not be solidified. This solid or oil was redissolved in fresh petroleum ether (20 c.c.) and treated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) and refluxed for 12 hours. The dark chocolate complex, after filtration, was decomposed by ice and HCl (conc.). The yellowish white substance, thus obtained, dissolves in dilute caustic soda on warming, forming a greenish solution and is precipitated by HCl as a curdy white solid, quickly becoming reddish due to oxidation. The yield is poor. The caustic soda solution with potassium ferricyanide produces a bluish violet precipitate of the bis-indigo with poor yield. For condensation with *o*-diketones, the acetic acid solution of the crude thioindoxyl has been used in all cases.

2-(4:5-*Fluorenothiophene*)-3'-*indol-indigo* (IIa) was prepared by mixing an acetic acid solution of (I) with a solution of isatin in acetic acid and adding 5 drops of HCl (conc.). Immediately the solution became pink and a violet precipitate separated out. The mixture was heated for half an hour to ensure complete reaction and filtered hot, the residue washed with acetic acid and alcohol and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a violet crystalline mass, m.p. above 300°. It dissolves slightly in alkaline hydrosulphite with a yellow colour and dyes cotton in light pink shade. In H_2SO_4 (conc.) it dissolves with a violet colour. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 3.5. $C_{22}H_{12}O_2NS$ requires C, 75.2; H, 3.5 per cent).

2-(4:5-*Fluorenothiophene*)-3'-(6'-*bromo*)-*indol-indigo* (IIb), -3'-(5': 7'-*dinitro*)-*indol-indigo* (IIc), -2'-*acenaphthylene-indigo* (IId), -2'-(5' or 6'-*bromo*)-*acenaphthylene-indigo* (IIe), -2'-(5' or 6'-*nitro*)-*acenaphthylene-indigo* (IIf), -2'-(5': 6'-*dinitro*)-*acenaphthylene-indigo* (IIg), -9'-*phenanthrene-indigo* (IIh), -1'-*aceanthrylene-indigo* (IIi) were similarly prepared as compound (IIa) with the corresponding *o*-diketones (vide Table I). The dyes were crystallised from nitrobenzene. The m.p. of the compounds, crystalline shape, colour in H_2SO_4 (conc.), dyeing shade on cotton from hydrosulphite vat and mol. formula and analysis are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Dye No.	<i>o</i> -Diketone.	M. P.	Colour & crystal shape.	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄ .	Shade on cotton.	Formula.	Analysis Found.	Calc.
IIb	<i>m</i> -Bromoisatin	> 300*	Dark violet mass	Light green	Light violet	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ NBrS	C: 61.65% H: 2.87	61.88% 2.69
IIc	5:7-Dinitroisatin	Do	Greyish violet cryst. mass	Green	Chocolate violet	C ₂₃ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₂ S	N: 8.9	9.19
IIId	Acenaphthenequinone	Do*	Copper-red needles	Do	Violet	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ O ₂ S	C: 80.3 H: 3.5	80.6 3.48
IIe	5-Bromoacenaphthenequinone	Do†	Violet needles	Do	Do	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ BrS	C: 67.18 H: 2.9	67.36 2.7
IIIf	5-Nitro- Do	Do	Dark mass	Light green	Light blue	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ NS	C: 72.31 H: 3.2	72.48 2.97
IIg	5:6-Dinitro- Do	Do	Do	Violet	Green	C ₂₇ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₂ S	N: 5.72	5.69
IIh	Phenanthrenequinone	Do	Do	Chocolate-violet	Light violet	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ S	C: 80.93 H: 3.91	81.30 3.73
IIi	Aceanthraquinone	Do	Chocolate mass	Chocolate brown	Light brown	C ₃₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ S	C: 82.13 H: 3.65	82.3 3.54

* Shrinking at 290°.

† Subliming at high temp.

2-(4:5-*Fluorenothiophene*)-*ethylene-indigo* (III) was prepared by heating fluorenohydroxythiophene and glyoxal sodium bisulphite in acetic acid solution with the addition of 10 c.c. HCl (conc.), when gradually it separated out as a violet precipitate. It was obtained as a violet crystalline powder from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 300°. It dissolves in H₂SO₄ (conc.) with a violet colour and dyes cotton from brown hydrosulphite vat in light bluish violet shade. (Found: C, 81.43; H, 2.91. C₂₂H₁₇O₂S₂ requires C, 81.78; H, 2.87 per cent).

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